

TOWARDS A CASHLESS ZIMBABWE: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

This study seeks to empirically examine the benefits and convenience of the cashless economy in Zimbabwe. To achieve its objectives, the study employed a qualitative research approach, in which accidental sampling technique was employed. The results indicate that the emergence of the cashless economy paradigm in Zimbabwe has posed benefits to economic agents. However, results also indicate that cashless payment platforms in Zimbabwe are not yet efficient as anticipated. Amongst other policy prescriptions, the study recommends the provision of necessary infrastructural facilities such as POS vending machines that support and facilitate the smooth flow of the cashless society.

Key Words: Cashless economy, electronic payment systems, information technology, Zimbabwe

I. INTRODUCTION

The recent evolution in technology for financial transactions poses interesting questions for policy makers and financial institutions regarding the suitability of current institutional arrangements and availability of instruments to guarantee financial stability, efficiency and effectiveness of monetary policy. Over the course of history, different forms of payment systems have been in existence as a framework for exchange [9]. The advancement of information technology has facilitated innovation in electronic payment where goods and services are traded without the use of physical cash [6]. A cash economy is defined by [21] as one where, most of the time, cash is used to do purchases and transactions while a cashless economy or society is one where, most of the time, purchases and transactions are done by either electronic transfers or the cheque system. A cashless economy, as noted by [12], describes an economic state where financial transactions are not conducted with money in form of physical bank notes or coins, but through the transfer of digital information between the transacting parties. A cashless payment system, according to [6], eliminates the usage of money as a medium of exchange for goods and services by allowing electronic transfer payments or non-electronic payment via cheques. Nowadays credit & debit cards, RTGS, as well as online payment services like PayPal and WebMoney are increasingly becoming famous in Zimbabwe, especially in the urban areas where

there is higher access to internet.

The cashless economy, driven by the credit card system and operations enhances a window of improved efficient economic financial flow with the least hiccups and facilitates a proper tracking of cash flows in the banking system. It is very convenient at all times and for all transactions, and also reduces waste of resources both for the consumers on one part and the government on the other part. The cashless system in all economies where it is being operated (like Kenya, Pakistan and other developing countries) promotes efficiency in the economic services due to the reduced time of the entire transaction compared with deals that involve counting of currencies in the banks for several hours [20]. [21] discuss various advantages of the cashless economy such as faster transactions, increased sales, easy cash collection, inflation management and job creation amongst others.

Throughout the world there is considerable interest amongst policy makers and academicians to explore the possibility of moving towards a cashless economy. However, in most economies, including Zimbabwe, cash still remains the main form of transaction. In Zimbabwe, particularly, the amount of cash transactions is likely to go down, following the emergence of the cashless economy paradigm which is now unstoppable. In fact, there is ample evidence to prove that physical cash is slowly vanishing in many economies. The year 2017 marked yet another decrease in the amount of bank notes and coins in circulation in the Zimbabwean economy. [17], [19], [21] and [22] have already stressed the fact that Zimbabwe is currently facing a serious cash crisis. Although there are a plethora of reasons that can definitely explain this scenario, it is generally acknowledged that the cashless economy paradigm is fast gaining ground. However, the popularity of the cashless economy hype is not the same in all nations. There are countries which are still finding it difficult to adapt to the electronic money transfer systems. In Zimbabwe, it is yet to be "really" known why it seems difficult to embrace the cashless economy.

Statement of the Problem

The emergence of the cashless economy is supposed to ease flow of business transactions and improve financial stability of the economy and yet it has resulted in the woes of several economic agents. Most economic agents now lament over their productive time wasted in bank queues. Depositors also complain over "unreasonable" transaction costs, especially on withdrawals. The operation of the cashless economy in Zimbabwe is currently inefficient as evidenced by large numbers of people who complain about the adoption of plastic money and other cashless economy facilities. Only 33% of Zimbabwe's population lives in urban areas, the rest lives in rural areas and yet there are either few cashless payment systems or there is no access to internet. 5% of the rural population, as asserted by [16], has access to banking facilities; so the teething problem is that the majority of the population is financially excluded.

Now, it leaves a lot to be desired, especially in terms of asserting the “real” benefits of the cashless economy revolution. [21] noted that Zimbabwe’s preparedness to adopt the cashless economy is currently on a low profile. Therefore, there is need to also uncover the reasons why economic agents are not yet willing to fully embrace the cashless economy in Zimbabwe.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate the benefits of the cashless economy in the context of Zimbabwe. The study also sought to uncover reasons why Zimbabweans are not yet willing to fully embrace the cashless economy initiative.

Research Questions

- i. What is a cashless economy?
- ii. What are the benefits of a cashless economy in Zimbabwe?
- iii. How convenient are the cashless facilities in Zimbabwe?
- iv. Why are economic agents not yet willing to fully embrace the cashless economy in Zimbabwe?

Significance of the Study

The importance of this study is hinged on the premise that if the benefits of the cashless economy are illuminated, it can be much easier to convince Zimbabweans on the need to fully embrace the cashless economy initiative. The study also envisages to categorically sensitize policy makers in Zimbabwe on the need to come up with a fully operational cashless policy that will see improvements in the efficiency of the electronic payment systems.

Limitations

Considering the relatively small size of the sample used, the results of this research may suffer limited generalizability.

Delimitations

The study was restricted to investigating the benefits of the cashless economy, its convenience and why it is not being fully embraced. The target population was delimited to respondents (traders, civil servants and university students) in Harare only. Other potential respondents (those that could have been included) like economists; lawyers as well as politicians were outside the purview of this research.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Literature Review

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

Initially proposed by [8], this is one of the commonly used models in explaining how information technology is gradually adopted or accepted by people. The TAM is hinged on basically two beliefs and these are perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEU) of innovation. These beliefs, according to this theory, play a pivotal role in the technology acceptance behavior of individuals. TAM, as noted by [24] and [3] is a multivariable technology acceptance theory that predicts the users’ intention on the basis of their perception. The fundamental implication of the TAM is that attitudes predict intentions, and intentions predict behavior. The main argument of this model is that adoption is an outcome of intention which is determined through the usefulness and ease of use of a technology. The dimensions of TAM thus include usefulness, ease of use, attitude to use, intention to use and actual use. TAM, as already noted by [5], is well known as a highly predictive model with simplicity in term of variables. A plethora of authors e.g [13], [27] and [24], highlight the fact that the TAM has gained overwhelming acceptance and applicability in theory and policy, especially regarding the adoption of information technology. The TAM is diagrammatically illustrated below:

Figure 1

In this case, the TAM implies that economic agents will accept the cashless economy based on their perceived usefulness of the cashless payment systems as well as their perceived ease of use of the cashless payment systems. These perceptions play a crucial role in people's attitudes and behavioral intentions to use the electronic payment systems

The Theory of Payment System Efficiency and Central Bank Monopoly

The advocates of the theory of payment system efficiency and central bank monopoly, [7] assert

that the central bank is poised to lose its monopoly position in the provision of liquidity as the economy moves towards a cashless society. The authors further argue that the increased adoption of cashless banking instruments is beneficial in the sense that it strengthens and consolidates monetary policy effectiveness.

Empirical Literature Review

[11] examined the fundamental relationship between the adoption of electronic retail payments and overall economic growth across 27 European countries from the period 1995-2009 and they found out that movement to an effective electronic retail payment would stimulate the overall economic growth, consumption and trade. [14] analysed the acceptance of e-banking in Nigeria and found out that acceptance of e-banking in Nigeria was significantly influenced by age, educational background, income, personal benefits, perceived ease of use, perceived risk and perceived enjoyment. [18] investigated bankers' perceptions of electronic banking in Nigeria. Their results indicate that bankers in Nigeria perceive electronic banking as a tool for minimizing inconvenience, reducing transaction costs, altering customers' queuing pattern and saving customers' banking time. [2] investigated the impact of mobile banking on service delivery in Nigerian commercial banks and found out that the introduction of e-banking services has improved banking effectiveness in offering services to clients.

[23] investigated the appraisal of the cashless economy policy in the development of the Nigerian economy and found out that: most Nigerians are already aware of the policy and majority agrees that the policy will help fight against corruption or money laundering and reduce the risk of carrying cash. [28] investigated whether the long term shift to credit and debit cards stimulates economic growth of 56 countries worldwide and their results show that electronic card payments can increase efficiency and boost consumption of the economy. [4] analysed the effect of cashless monetary policy on Nigerian banking industry and found that there are significant reasons and benefits inherent in the implementation of the cashless policy. The study also showed that the cashless policy positively affected the development of banks; as it facilitates ease of operations and reduces queues and congestion in the banking hall. [1] looked at cashless policy and customers' satisfaction with special reference to commercial banks in Ogun State in Nigeria. Their results show that the cashless policy contributes significantly to customers' satisfaction in Ogun State, through electronic channels. [26] analysed cashless payments and economic growth in 5 European Union (EU) countries, namely, Austria, Belgium, France, Germany and Portugal; for the period 2000-2012. They found that there is a short-run causality running from cheque payment to telegraphic transfer and card payment, as well as causality running from telegraphic transfer to card payment; and that in the long-run, there is a significant effect of adopting cashless payment on the economies of the 5 EU countries.

Research Gap

Empirical evidence (reviewed) in this study is originating from other countries such as

Nigeria, Germany and France amongst others. These studies may suffer limited applicability in the Zimbabwean context due to variations in economic status, technology adoption levels, political and governance issues, life styles as well as consumer preferences. There is no similar empirical study that has been done in Zimbabwe. This research gap makes it even more inevitable to carry out a study of this nature in Zimbabwe. It is envisaged that policy makers and other relevant stakeholders will gain more benefits from this study in terms of getting a comprehensive policy prescription, based on latest empirical evidence.

III. METHODS & MATERIALS

This research was conducted using accidental sampling technique, in Harare, the capital city of Zimbabwe. A closed ended questionnaire was used as a data collection instrument. Structured interviews were also done to complement questionnaires. A total of 700 questionnaires were distributed to three categories of respondents, namely Traders, Students (Undergraduate Students in local universities) and Civil Servants. Only 567 questionnaires were completed and analyzed, giving a response rate of 81%, as shown in the table below:

Table 1

Returned	567	81
Returned but not properly filled	0	0
Not returned	133	19
Total distributed	700	100

IV. RESULTS

Demographics

Respondents' gender

Responses on gender indicate that male respondents accounted for approximately 48% (that is, 270) while female respondents accounted for approximately 52% (that is, 297).

Figure 2 Respondents' gender

Figure 3 *Age of Respondents*

The illustration above shows that most respondents (47%) were aged between 26 and 35. This represents part of the most economically active population in Zimbabwe.

Occupation of respondents

Figure 5

Most of the respondents, were traders (209), followed by civil servants (195) and lastly students (165).

Benefits of cashless economy in Zimbabwe

Table 2

Increase employment	249
Reduce cash related robbery	374
Reduce cash related corruption	436
Attract more foreign investment	198
Faster transactions	470
Reduced costs	85
Increased sales	368
Easy cash collection	419
Easy clearance of goods	402
Reduces bank queues	45
Improves credit availability	289
Reduces inflation	391

Most respondents (470, that is 83%) opined that the cashless economy is beneficial in the sense that it facilitates faster transactions. 77% of the respondents thought that the cashless economy is beneficial in terms of reducing cash-related corruption. In fact the table above actually shows that the most five perceived benefits of the cashless economy in Zimbabwe are: faster transactions, reduction in cash-related corruption, easy cash collection, ease clearance of goods at customs offices and reduction of inflation. However, there are also other benefits of the cashless economy that have also been identified by the respondents are these are: increase sales,

improves credit availability, reduce cash related robbery, increase employment, attract more foreign investment, reduced costs and reduces bank queues, in their chronological order. Of interest, only 8% of the respondents opined that the cashless economy reduces bank queues!

Figure 6 : *Convenience of usage of cashless facilities in Zimbabwe*

As shown in the graph above, a substantial proportion (54%) of respondents considered the cashless economy in Zimbabwe as a very difficult way of doing business.

Reasons for not willing to fully embrace the cashless economy

Figure 7

As shown in the graph above, most economic agents in Zimbabwe are not willing to fully embrace the cashless economy initiative precisely because the cashless payment facilities are not available everywhere, especially in rural areas. This is evidenced by 96% of the respondents who

opined that cashless platforms are not available everywhere and therefore they are not willing to embrace the cashless economy revolution. However, it is important to note that other reasons include high cost of access, high service charge or transaction costs, lack of knowledge or skill, safe to use cash, increase spending, as well as prone to error.

Discussion

Overall findings of this study indicate that the cashless economy in Zimbabwe is beneficial. The emergence of the cashless economy in Zimbabwe has brought about the following benefits to economic agents: faster transactions, reduction in cash related corruption, easy cash collection and reduction in cash related robbery amongst other benefits. These findings generally confirm the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) in the sense that economic agents in Zimbabwe perceive benefits of the cashless economy and on such grounds there is a higher possibility of overwhelming adoption levels especially in the next coming few years, as the cashless economy paradigm becomes more and more popular. The findings of this study also confirm [7]’s (2001) theory of payment system efficiency and central bank monopoly; in the sense that it has been revealed that the cashless economy reduces inflation, thereby strengthening and consolidating monetary policy effectiveness. This is very true and acceptable in the Zimbabwean context because inflation is currently hovering at a monthly average of 2%.

Specifically, the findings of this study revealed that the cashless economy is beneficial in the sense that it enhances faster transactions. This shows that economic agents in Zimbabwe understand that, all things being equal, cashless payment systems ought to speed up the transaction processes. These findings are consistent with the findings of [18] who found out that electronic banking in Nigeria saves customers’ banking time. The results also confirm the analysis of [21] who opined that the cashless society enhances faster transactions. The findings of this study also indicate that the other benefit of the cashless economy is that it plays a pivotal role in reduction of cash related corruption and cash related robbery. These findings are consistent with the findings of [23] who found that in Nigeria the cashless economy helps fight against corruption or money laundering and reduce the risk of carrying cash; these findings also confirm the observation by [21] that the cashless economy reduces the incidence of corruption, money laundering and cash related robbery.

Furthermore, the study also found out that the cashless economy is beneficial in the sense that it facilitates easy cash collection and easy clearance of goods (at Customs Offices). While these findings confirm the observation by [21], they are also consistent with the findings of [4] whose study showed that in Nigeria, the cashless policy positively affected the development of banks; as it facilitates ease of operations, reduces queues and congestion in banking halls. The study also found out that the cashless economy reduces inflation. This confirmed [21]’s argument that cashless economy facilitates a smooth control over inflationary

pressures. Moreso, the study also found out that the cashless economy increases sales for traders. This is acceptable as it confirms previous studies of [11] and [28] whose studies indicate that the cashless payment systems such as cards increase consumption, implying that sales also go up due to increased card usage. The study also indicates that the cashless economy can improve credit availability in the economy. This is consistent with the observation by [21] that the cashless economy ensures that banks have excess liquidity that can be used as credit to both public and private investment sectors.

However, the study also paradoxically found that few respondents (15%) opine that the cashless economy reduces costs, which means that most people assert that cashless payment systems have resulted in an escalation in transaction charges. It has also been shown that few respondents (8%) opine that the cashless economy reduces bank queues, implying that most respondents view the cashless payment facilities as a “delay mechanism” in their day to day business. Although this is contrary to the findings of [18] and [4], it is consistent with the observation by [21] who have already noted that in Zimbabwe, queues at banks have become a common feature; and that transaction costs are currently too high.

The study also revealed that cashless payment facilities in Zimbabwe “complicate” the way of doing business as evidenced by 54% of the respondents who opined that the cashless economy in Zimbabwe is a very difficult way of doing business. This can be attributed to the fact that, as noted by [21] Zimbabwe has been a cash based economy for a long period of time. Most people are finding it difficult to adjust to the new ways of doing business. The other fact that can as well explain this situation is that Zimbabwe economy is mostly informal; and unbanked. Zimbabwe already has a poor ranking in terms of the Ease of Doing Business (EDB) index. [22] noted that, based on the World Bank (2017) Easy of Doing Business index, Zimbabwe is ranked 161; down from 156 last year, out of 190 countries; where a ranking of 1 is considered the most conducive environment for doing business. Last, but not least, the study also shows that basically there are 4 reasons why economic agents are not willing to embrace the cashless economy and these are: cashless platforms not available everywhere, high cost of access (businesses lament over high costs of acquiring Point of Sale machines), high service charges as well as lack of knowledge and skill as already highlighted in [21].

V. CONCLUSION

The study focused on 3 categories of respondents, that is; traders, students and civil servants. Owing to their vast experience and involvement in business and financial transactions, more traders were sampled. Also important to note, is the fact that the highest number of respondents is within the age bracket of 26-35, which forms the largest part of the economically active Zimbabweans (or the working population) who are not only youthful but also engaged into businesses. This consolidates the reliability of the findings. This study generally indicates that the emergence of the cashless economy era in Zimbabwe is actually beneficial. However, the

efficiency of the operation of the cashless payment systems needs to be improved in order to address bottlenecks especially at banking halls. The existence of a cashless economy in Zimbabwe, as already noted by [21], may end up achieving unintended results especially when responsible authorities do not put enough infrastructure that support the cashless economy.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. The government, in collaboration with the private sector, should engage on thorough awareness campaigns in order to enlighten economic agents about the benefits of a cashless economy
- ii. To ensure a properly functional cashless economy, there should be adequate infrastructural facilities in place, for instance Point of Sale (POS) machines as well as Automated Teller Machines (ATMs)
- iii. The central bank, since it is the apex bank; should continuously intervene to reduce transaction charges for using cashless economy platforms and facilities such as cards amongst others
- iv. The government, just like what is happening in other African countries such as Nigeria, should ideally come up with a cashless policy in order to properly administer the operationalization of the cashless economy in Zimbabwe

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